

Map Enhancers or Map Monsters: Do cartographic embellishment choices matter for teaching in higher education?

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Summary

Technological and data progress has significantly increased our ability to create and use maps as educational resources across disciplines. While it is now possible to develop maps easily without much thought, that doesn't mean we shouldn't think about our cartographic design choices. This work looks at the aspect of chart junk, or graphic embellishments (via symbols, pictures, icons) on maps. A randomised control study of students was used to collect data preferences and whether chart junk is seen as auxiliary design or superfluous ornamentation. Data on information recall from a series of treatment control trials is collected and analysed alongside open-ended preference discussions.

KEYWORDS: Map design; Cartography; Chart junk; Pedagogy

1. Introduction

There's a long history of using graphic design and visual embellishments on maps to convey information (Spence and Wainer, 2005; Harley, 2001). From the iconography and symbology of early religious maps and mediaeval *Mappa Mundis*, the inclusion of 'map monsters' or large sea monsters often as warnings in discovery-era navigation maps, to modern map-infographics with detailed information or statistics added alongside.

The overall design of data visuals is important for more than just preferences (Montello, 2002; Spence, 2006). Including additional elements (e.g. text boxes, icons, stylistic features, pictures) has been argued to hinder the transfer of core information (Rop *et al.*, 2018), but also potentially making the visual more memorable (Bateman *et al.*, 2010). This is important in cartography as effective maps need to simultaneously communicate high dimensional information and consider the most effective way to do this visually (Karssen, 1980; Field and Demaj, 2012; Robinson *et al.*, 2017).

2. Methodology and Data Collection

We use a randomised trial of students from the School of Geography and Planning (University of Sheffield) to collect primary quantitative data on map recollection and open-ended preference discussions related to visual embellishments. A series of five different map questionnaires (trials) were given to participants asking them to consider, comment and recall information from a visual.

Some (control) participants received one version of a map while others (treated) received an equivalent map in all respects except for additional 'chart junk'. Students were given time to look at a map and then asked the same questions. Surveys were randomised across students both in terms of receiving a control (plain) or treated (embellished) map, and by which map of the five they answered questions about in which order. **Figure 1** outlines the data collection and randomisation for a participant with trials labelled A to E.

Figure 1: Project (Questionnaire) Design Flow Chart

2.1. Map design

Maps represented abstract locations and hypothetical names. Most sets of maps consisted of a control (plain) and a treated (embellished) version. Two of the trial rounds only had plain versions of the map. With treated and control map sets, both had the same exact design, placements and information. The first was rather plain, the second embellished with various types of design features. The different embellishments were drawn from various inspiration and tried to capture a range of contexts (historic navigation maps, hiking maps, planning and development, urban networks, etc.). Each map had an associated short text of equal length giving some background information and context. This remained the same for both versions of the map. The maps and respective story for *Trial A* is in **Figure 2** with the remaining detailed in the **Appendix**.

2.2. Survey development and participants

Each map had a questionnaire, equivalent for control and treated participants. Different trials were ordered randomly, and participants allocated a unique sequence of surveys ensuring they all completed each trial once and randomly allocated a control or treated map. A Google Script was coded to randomly allocate questionnaire link sequences to participant allowing for additional participation online. Ten participants came for the in-person data collection and an additional 8 online. While relatively low individual turnout, each participant completed each trial with multiple questions.

Participants spent 2-3 minutes with a map before progressing to the next screen for a series of generic questions. Following this, participants proceeded to a series of map specific questions asking them to remember some of the key names, features or layouts from the map they had seen two screens prior.

3. Analysis and Discussion

3.1. Thematic analysis

After finishing questions related to maps option participants were asked to comment on both sets of maps through open-ended questions. There seemed to be stronger preference for plain maps when it came to needing information and details, compared to the more embellished versions. **Table 2** summarises some salient keywords from across the comments.

Figure 2: Maps Group A

Map A1: Moderately Plain

Map A2: Embellished

Accompanying Text:

“The City of Coral boasts one of the deepest natural harbours in the world at around 55 feet. While this has led to great trade and prosperity for the city, the strong currents have also led to the famous seven sunken wrecks of Coral Harbour. At points of the year, the waves of the harbour can be very dangerous, and oftentimes the harbour must be closed for transit.”

Table 2: Keyword Analysis

PLAIN MAP	
POSITIVE	NEGATIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct • Less busy • Less effort to read • Clarity • No distractive elements • Easy to understand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacks imagery • Boring • Blank space
EMBELISHED MAP	
POSITIVE	NEGATIVE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visually appealing • More illustration • Adds context • Easier to understand • Legends are more obvious • Adds to the general aesthetic 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distracting • Cluttered • Hard to comprehend • Confusing • Crowded • Noisy

Some discussed the unnecessary addition of images to the maps and that there should only be the minimum required additional features when trying to convey information. The themes of clutter and distractions were brought up regularly.

“The map already contains so much information, the addition of the ‘images’ doesn’t add anything in particular, it just works to clutter it.”
- Male; 25-29; PGT Student

Given that participants were aware the goal was on information recall, many comments discussed these graphic enhancements as unimportant for the information in the map. Even so, among comments, there was the broad impression that embellished versions were more visually stimulating, interesting and ‘pretty’. Notably, some discussed how the maps with these added features allowed them to interpret the map without having to rely only on text.

“<The Embellished Map> doesn’t just rely on words to convey information so it is less effort to read, yet it is not overly cluttered.”
- Male; 20-24; UG Student

Having visual embellishments that act as supporting context or information on a map was brought up many times. Where visual embellishments complemented the information on the map, there seemed to be a more positive discussion around it (e.g. comparing the discussion around embellishments on Map C where they are symbols for local amenities versus Map A where they are pure graphic enhancements). This point was particularly important for users reading a map in a foreign language or context.

“The symbols provide a useful bit of context, and for non-English speakers would help to bridge a gap in understanding”
- Male; 25-29; PGT Student

Overall, there was stronger preference for the embellished maps in C and D compared to A (65% and 71% preferred compared to 17%). There were also very high percentage of respondents suggesting C and D had the most information on the actual map itself (100% and 94%), and a high percent of trial A respondents thinking the embellished version was more informative (61%). With Trials C and D having embellishments which are linked to enhancing the information rather than just graphic in nature, these results are telling about what is important in our design.

3.2. Statistical analysis

Using data on relative percentage of correct questions associated to each map, we can explore more formal correlations and whether there are significant differences in outcomes conditional on a given map having added embellishments.

An OLS regression is estimated in **Table 3** under the principle of comparing scores associated to participants looking at control maps and those looking at embellished treated maps. By specifying this model and controlling for other confounding variables which might impact outcomes (i.e. individual characteristics; ordering of trials), we are able to get more robust evidence and values associated to outcomes of chart junk.

The estimated model is:

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T_i + \beta_2 P_i + \beta_3 O_i + \varepsilon_i$$

y_i represents the percentage scored in each map trial; T_i represents an indicator (0, 1) for whether the map was ‘embellished’ or not; P_i are participant fixed-effects to control for individual differences and capturing most of the heterogeneity; and O_i controlling for the ordering of trials.

Table 3: OLS Analysis

<i>Dep. Variable = Percent Map Recollection Questions Correct</i>	
Variable	Estimate (p-value)
(Intercept)	64.16*** (0.0000)
Treated Map Effect	- 10.15* (0.0776)
Trial Order Effect	1.30 (0.4509)
<i>Participant Fixed Effects</i>	Yes
<i>N</i>	85
<i>R-squared</i>	0.2093
<i>F-statistic</i>	2.184 (0.0103)

These correlations indicate a negative impact of embellishments in terms of outcomes of information recall. The treated versions on average correlate with an approximate 10% decrease in scores. This is a relatively large effect, and while in part driven by the low number of questions in each round, does indicate potential detrimental impacts from too much chart clutter.

4. Concluding Remarks

There are no definite net positive or negative associations that can be made for visual embellishment from the data collected. Participants highlighted the visual interest added by some of these graphic design choices, but also discussed the fine line between enhancement and clutter. Statistical evidence

suggests while there might be a slight preference for more visually appealing embellished maps, there is significant negative correlation to map information recall.

From this work, there are four key **highlights** we take away relevant for map design:

1. The purpose of the map matters. Users know beforehand what they need a map for, and this will impact their use of it (i.e. if they know they need information out of it, they might find embellishments a distraction; if the map is for artistic purposes, this would be different).
2. There is a fine line between the inclusion of embellishments and clutter. In two of map trials (C, D), participants preferred embellished versions and commented highly on it; while in the third (A) they felt that the images were distracting.
3. Where visual embellishments complemented information on the map, there seemed to be more positive discussion around it. This can be particularly the case when users are reading/ using a map in a foreign language or uncommon context.
4. Measuring quantitative outcomes is difficult at the aggregate, and a more detailed classification of the mechanisms by which graphic features contribute or detract from the information is important to consider.

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Biographies

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Appendix: Trial Maps

Table A1: Map Trials Overview

Trial	Context	Plain	Embellishment
A	The 7 Famous Sunken Wrecks of Coral Harbour	Harbour city, downtown roads and information on harbour depth.	Addition of old-style nautical icons – ships, sea creatures, mermaids.
B	Hiking the Grantchester Peak-to-Peak Trail	Map outlining a hiking path on the outskirts of Grantchester.	
C	New Residential and Retail Development – The Meadows	Map showing location of new housing development and local amenities.	Addition of amenities icons in the style of city navigation maps.
D	Burger-Fest 2024 Restaurant Rota	City map with circular route being directed between a set of restaurants.	Addition of graphic food pictures for each burger stop.
E	A Proposed City Centre Pedestrian Strategy	Proposed pedestrianisation strategy and streets that would be pedestrianised.	

Figure A1: Map Group B

Figure A2: Map Group C

Accompanying Text:

“A new small development is being proposed in the urban centre, and it is said to be a prime location. Residents here will find themselves within walking distance to a range of amenities including transit stops, the civic centre, theatres, restaurants and more. New retail areas are also being proposed for small outdoor shopping plazas.”

Figure A3: Map Group D

Accompanying Text:

“Introducing the 2024 Burger-Fest Rota, hosted by six of the city's premier burger restaurants. This year, the restaurants are offering 30% discounts and the chance to win free burger vouchers for a year by collecting specialty cards at each location. Added bonus prizes will be available for anyone able to eat at each of the restaurants and collect a card within a week.”

Figure A4: Map Group E

Map E1: Benchmarking Trial

Accompanying Text:

“Churlton high street has been undergoing dramatic declines in footfall and use in recent years. The city council is proposing a strategy to pedestrianise a segment of the main downtown using a set of bollards. The argument is to increase the attractiveness of the area and stimulate pedestrian activity. Many proponents argue that this might limit accessibility for many. What a debate!”